

PhyloRNA: a database of RNA secondary structures with associated phylogeny

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Abstract. The ability to access, search and analyse RNA molecules considering their secondary structures and their phylogenies can be useful in understanding the evolution of organisms. Although it is known that RNA structures are more conserved than sequences during evolution, no database easily links RNA secondary structures with the organism's taxonomies. In this work, we introduce PhyloRNA, a curated database containing a collection of known RNA secondary structures drawn from public databases. The structures are available in BPseq, CT, Dot-bracket and Fasta formats and are equipped with main existing taxonomies, such as SILVA, ENA, LTP, NCBI, and GTDB. Each RNA structure is also associated with structural features: the presence of pseudoknots, the number of paired and unpaired nucleotides and other abstractions. PhyloRNA is publicly available at <https://bdslab.unicam.it/phyloRNA/>.

1 Introduction

The number of RNA secondary structures has recently increased thanks to experimental tools such as X-rays and MNR or computational tools capable of predicting such structures starting from sequences. In the literature, many RNA databases store secondary structures. For example, the Rfam Database [1] stores non-coding RNA families, and the Comparative RNA Web Site (CRW) contains predicted secondary structures of ribosomal and intron RNA molecules [2]. The Sprinzl tRNA database [3], the RNase P database [4], and the tmRNA databases [5] store tRNA, RNase P RNA, and tmRNA molecules, respectively. There have been many attempts at creating RNA meta-databases, such as RNA STRAND and BpRNA [6,7].

It is well known that secondary structures are more conserved than sequences during organism evolution. However, their link with organisms' taxonomy can not be immediately reconstructed using existing databases. PhyloRNA aims at providing this link using main evolutionary taxonomies, i.e., SILVA [8], ENA [9], LTP [10], NCBI [11] and GTDB [12]. PhyloRNA can be considered a meta-database whose particular focus is to associate available curated phylogenetic information with the stored structures.

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PhyloRNA contains known RNA secondary structures associated with their phylogenetic information according to several curated taxonomies ([SILVA](#), [ENA](#), [LTP](#), [NCBI](#), [GTDB](#)) to allow the scientific community to study the relationship between RNA structures and phylogenetic ranks. In addition, structural features and abstractions of the structures are available.

Figure 1: PhyloRNA homepage

Figure 1 shows the homepage of the PhyloRNA website. It permits the download of RNA secondary structures in the BPseq, CT and Dot-Bracket formats or just the sequence in the FASTA format. In addition, to facilitate the parsing of the files, the user can download the molecules without their headers, which usually contains metadata without a structured scheme. PhyloRNA provides the capability to select the molecules considering their structural features, such as genus [14], pseudoknot order [15], pseudoknots structure or not, the number of paired and unpaired nucleotides, and some abstractions, including core, core-plus and shape, obtained by deleting or collapsing stacks [17]. Such structural features and abstractions can be interactively searched, visualized and downloaded. They can be used to study species evolution, to understand the structural abstractions common in a specific set of RNA molecules, or to evaluate RNA secondary structure prediction methods. The current release of PhyloRNA contains 21630 entries: 5S rRNA (3567), 16S rRNA (17625), 23S rRNA (158), Group I Intron (142) and Group II Intron (129) drawn from the public databases CRW and Rfam. The data will be continuously incremented with molecules drawn from other public databases, e.g., PDB [13], and other families will be included. The updated phylogenetic information released by the taxonomy websites will be synchronized with PhyloRNA. Updates of structures and phylogenies will be scheduled every six months, described in the “Changelog” section of the website.

2 Data and Methods

The current release of PhyloRNA contains RNA sequences and secondary structures of the following provenance:

1. Comparative RNA Web Site, version 2, enclosing entries of ribosomal and intronic RNA molecules whose secondary structure have been predicted by covariance-based comparative sequence analysis
2. Rfam Database, collection of RNA sequence families of structural RNAs including non-coding RNA genes as well as cis-regulatory elements.

To create the database, data were first collected from the external sources and then processed and prepared for being inserted in the NoSQL database MongoDB [16]. The web pages interact with the database for searching and recovering the molecules. In what follows we describe in detail the construction and content of each module.

Data processing. The data processing consists of creation of a Unique ID for each molecule, converting the available format into all others and determining structural features and abstractions.

Unique IDs. We created a unique for each entry in the PhyloRNA database. Future releases will keep all previous IDs un-changed.

Conversion scripts. One of the challenging tasks in collecting the data arose from the fact that the external sources do not offer data in all formats. We have used the tool TARNAS, implemented in our lab, to convert from molecules in the available format into all other formats.

Structural features and abstraction scripts. We have implemented a script to compute structural features, such as genus, and structural abstraction such as core, core plus and shape.

NoSQL database. All the data were inserted into the non-relational database MongoDB [16], designed to handle document-oriented storage. The documents, grouped into collections, are uniquely identified. Our database consists of two collections: `rna_sequences`, and `session`. The former contains the molecules with the associated information, whereas the latter is created when a user performs a search or download operation from the website. Each document in the `rna_sequences` contains some fields, including Organism name, Accession number, Length, Pseudoknotted, Pseudoknot order, Rna Family, Genus, Core, Core Plus, Shape, Is Validated, Reference database link, Benchmark ID, and Taxonomy. The Taxonomy field is of type array: each array element contains a nested document for the taxonomy classification. The first field states if the organism is classified or not for that specific taxonomy; if it is classified, each subsequent field of the document represents the taxonomic rank with its taxa. The files related to the secondary structure are stored in the GridFS collections, a MongoDB convention for storing large files. The web interface to PhyloRNA has been created using Flask, a micro-framework web written in Python [18].

3 Results

PhyloRNA contains 21630 RNA molecules of 5S rRNA, 16S rRNA, 23S rRNA, Intron I Group and Intron II Group families. This represents a considerable amount of data to study the phylogenies of organisms. The main functions of the web interface are searching, browsing, and downloading. Figure 2 shows the hierarchical structure of the website.

Searching and browsing. The user can specify one or more search criteria in a web-based form. The general criteria include RNA type (e.g., 5S rRNA), organism of origin (e.g., *E. coli*), external source (e.g., RCSB Protein Data Bank), length (in bases) or the number of paired nucleotides, the genus and the pseudoknot order, or the structural abstraction such as core, core plus and shape. Details on individual entries from the result list of any search can be displayed by clicking on the “More Information” column of the results table.

Downloading. The set of molecules selected via the search page can be downloaded in one of four supported formats: CT, BPSEQ, dot-bracket and FASTA, equipped with a CSV file that

contains the information related to the selected taxonomy and the structural features and abstraction.

Figure 2 Hierarchical structure of the PhyloRNA website

4 Conclusion

We have presented PhyloRNA, a database for RNA secondary structure data equipped with the main taxonomies of the corresponding organisms. Such information can be useful in phylogenetic studies and in understanding the relationships between RNA structure and function. We also expect to facilitate the evaluation of comparison methods of RNA secondary structures and the development of new approaches to assess secondary structure prediction methods. Our database is flexible and can be easily extended; it provides a web interface to support searches according to many criteria, including structural properties and abstractions.

The database is publicly accessible to the research community. As future work, other rRNAs and Introns molecules will be added by determining their secondary structures from the tridimensional configuration taken from the PDB database. Moreover, we will add other families of RNA molecules, such as tRNA or tmRNA, from other databases. Finally, we will add other structural features, including properties of secondary structure elements and the representation of secondary structures.

Conflict of interests

The authors should declare here any potential conflicts of interests.

Availability of data and software code (optional)

PhyloRNA is publicly available at <https://bdslab.unicam.it/phylorna/>.

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